

Studies on Non-conventional Oil Seeds : Search for New Sources of Edible and Industrial Oils

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The seeds of *Ougeinia dalbergioids* Benth. obtained from forest origin, were investigated for their fatty oil constituents and some applications of the oil to edible as well as industrial purposes like alkyd resins and other oil-derived products. An attempt has been made to prepare oil incorporated azoalkyd disperse dyes by step by step process of polymerisation, co-polymerisation, diazotisation and coupling with phenolic compounds. Prepared dyes were studied for application on polyester, nylon and wool fabrics as azo disperse dyes.

Ougeinia dalbergioids Benth.¹ (N.O. Legumiosae, Papilionaceae) is also known as *Ougeinia oojainensis* Roxb. and 'Sandam' in Hindi. This is a valuable timber tree and is native of India. *O. dalbergioids* is a common tree found in deciduous forests, sal forests and grows on a wide variety of soils. It is distributed in the outer Himalayas and sub-Himalayan tracts from Jammu to Bhutan in altitudes upto 1500 m and seen in the whole of northern and central India including many parts of Deccan peninsula. The tree is popular due to its economic and medicinal values². The bark of the tree finds application in the cure of various diseases and the leaves are used as fodder to cattle.

In the present work the seed oil of *O. dalbergioids* has been examined chemically with a view to find out new oil for nutritional and/or industrial purposes.

A subacute study for three months was carried out on albino rats to study the nutritive value of the fatty oil. The oil was also tested for some oil-modified alkyds and nitroalkyds by polymerisation and co-polymerisation by transesterification of oil glycerides with freshly prepared phthalic and nitrophthalic acid anhydrides. Oil-incorporated 3-azo/4-azoalkyd dyes were prepared from the corresponding nitro-substituted alkyds by reducing the nitro group, diazotisation and coupling with various phenolic compounds. The shades of dyes were tested by applying these on nylon, polyester and wool fabrics.

Results and Discussion

The dried and powdered *O. dalbergioids* seeds on solvent extraction yielded 10.0% greenish yellow fixed oil: sp. gr. (33°), 0.9078; refractive index (30°), 1.4670; acid value, 7.0096; sap. value, 207.0527; iodine value, 97.7662; acetyl value, 7.163; unsaponifiable matter, 1.69%, containing β -sitosterol, stigmasterol, lupeol and one unidentified hydrocarbon. The glc analysis of the methyl esters of mixed

fatty acids using the conditions: column, 2% DEGS, coated on chromosorb (80-100 mesh), column diameter, 6' x 1/8" ss; injection temperature, 220°; detector temperature, 300°; oven temperature, 205°; carrier gas, N₂; flame, H₂ (20-30 ml/min), were shown that the oil is a mixture of glycerides of palmitic 35.839, palmitoleic 3.982, stearic 12.941, oleic 43.380, linoleic 0.498, linolenic 2.464, arachidic 0.448 and behenic 0.448% acids. The oil is rich in oleic and palmitic acids.

Examination of the animals in the test group did not show any abnormal signs such as loss of hairs, scaly skin, scaly tail, etc. The consumption of water and food of the test group was similar to that of control group. Thus one can conclude that during the 60-day period of observations, no toxic effects for the *O. dalbergioids* oil were seen. The weight-gain of the two groups also seen to be identical. The cholesterol content was found to be 82.450 mg/100 ml blood serum and 0.302 g/100 g liver weight for *O. dalbergioids* oil while the respective values for groundnut oil were 80.730 mg/100 ml and 0.299 g/100 g. The cholesterol content of blood serum as well as liver was also identical in both the groups. Since there is no elevation in blood cholesterol value one can safely use *O. dalbergioids* seed oil as a source of dietary fat.

From the data of Table 1, 280° temperature was chosen for polymerisation. The results of Table 2 show that the density, refractive index, intrinsic viscosity and average molecular weight increases and unsaturation decreases with increase in reaction time upto 8.0 h and after that, the oil was converted into the gel form resulting from crosslinking. The observation of average molecular weight shows that mostly dimerisation of the oil took place upto 8.0 h bodying at 280°.

The ir spectra³ of the thermally polymerised oil at 280 ± 2° for different time durations, reveal decrease in the intensity of ethylenic C=C bands at 3015 cm⁻¹ and progressive increase in the intensity of the methylene band at 2930 cm⁻¹, indicating

TABLE 1—THERMAL POLYMERISATION OF THE OIL FOR DIFFERENT TIME AND TEMPERATURES

Sl. no.	Temp. °C	Heating time h	R.I.	I.V	Density	η dl g ⁻¹	\bar{M}_n
1.	R.T.	00.0	1.467 0	97.77	0.907 8	0.046	520
2.	250	20.0	1.476 0	56.12	0.915 6	0.073	780
3.	260	16.0	1.473 8	52.73	0.919 3	0.077	842
4.	270	10.0	1.472 2	53.18	0.918 7	0.075	810
5.	280	06.0	1.475 0	48.30	0.923 8	0.078	868
6.	300	03.0	Gel product				

TABLE 2—THERMAL POLYMERISATION OF OIL AT 280 ± 2°

Sl. no.	Heating time h	R.I.	Density	I.V.	η dl g ⁻¹	K^*	\bar{M}_n
1.	0.0	1.467 0	0.907 8	97.77	0.046	...	520
2.	2.0	1.469 2	0.916 6	54.00	0.055	0.0006	585
3.	4.0	1.472 0	0.919 0	50.58	0.063	0.000C	725
4.	6.0	1.475 0	0.923 8	48.30	0.078	0.0006	868
5.	8.0	1.481 0	0.929 4	47.00	0.093	0.0006	1097
6.	Between 8.0 to 9.5 h			Gel product			

* K (bodying rate constant).

decrease in the number of *cis*-double bonds and hence progressive polymerisation is observed with increase in treatment time. The band observed at 1 470–1 460 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the C–H bending vibrations of the methylene group. As the polymerisation proceeds, these bands becomes progressively intense. The weakest absorption at 918 cm⁻¹ observed in the oil is due to isolated *cis* C=C as well as conjugated *trans-trans* –C=C–C=C–, which is evident from the presence of bands at 955 and 988 cm⁻¹ respectively. The band at 725 cm⁻¹ is due to CH₂ rocking vibrations, the intensity of which increases progressively as the polymerisation proceeds.

The ir spectra of *O. dalbergioides* oil modified 3-nitro- and 4-nitroalkyd resins show the symmetrical and asymmetrical stretching vibrations of C–NO₂ group at around 1 540 and 1 345 cm⁻¹ respectively as strong bands⁴. The strong intensity of these bands proves that in the alkyd resin, the nitrophthalic acid units are incorporated repeatedly.

The observation of Table 3 shows that the oil-modified alkyd and 3-/4-nitro-substituted alkyd resins form transparent, opaque and opaque films and number average molecular weight is 1310, 1420 and 1540 respectively (by VPO in CCl₄ solvent at 35°). All alkyd resins takes > 48 h for drying. The water-resistance (for 25 h) and acid-resistance (for 0.5 h) properties are good but the resistivity against alkali and some organic solvents viz. carbon tetrachloride, acetone, xylene, etc. (for 10 min) is poor. These alkyds may find use in paints and varnish type surface coating materials.

The ir spectra of reduced products of 3-nitro- and 4-nitroalkyd resins (sodium bicarbonate insoluble part) show medium broad band due to bonded NH₂ at around 3 450 cm⁻¹. On acetylation of the amino group, this band gets weakened. The reduction of nitro group was again tested from the remarkable

TABLE 3—PHYSICAL DATA OF ALKYD RESINS MODIFIED WITH THE OIL.*

Property	A	B	C
Appearance of the resin	Reddish brown	Brownish black	Brownish black
Nature of the film	Transparent	Opaque	Opaque
Acid value	22.2	26.6	24.7
Iodine value	33.0	37.0	31.0
Refractive index ($n_D^{25^\circ}$)	1.5059	1.5073	1.5082
Intrinsic viscosity (η , dl g ⁻¹)	0.107	0.111	0.115
Av. mol. wt. (\bar{M}_n)	1310	1420	1540
Drying time of the film (h)	> 48	> 48	> 48
Effect of water for 24 h	NE	NE	NE
Effect of 2% H ₂ SO ₄ for 30 min	NE	NE	NE
Effect of 5% NaOH for 30 min	PD	PD	PD
Effect of CCl ₄ for 10 min	TD	TD	TD
Effect of acetone for 10 min	PD	PD	PD
Effect of xylene for 10 min	PD	PD	PD

* (A)=Alkyd resin with phthalic anhydride; (B)=alkyd resin with 3-nitrophthalic anhydride; (C)=alkyd resin with 4-nitrophthalic anhydride.

NE≡No effect. PD≡Partially dissolved. TD≡Totally dissolved.

feature of amino alkyds. The alcoholic solutions of the aminoalkyds show slight fluorescence in uv-light. The corresponding acetyl derivatives did not show fluorescence. The ir spectra of 3-azoalkyd dye shows stretching vibrations at around 1 630, 1 600 and 1 512 cm⁻¹ which were not seen in the case of amino and *N*-acetylated-amino alkyds. The characteristic frequencies of oil observed at 1 000–900 cm⁻¹ are due to *cis-trans* isomerism.

The 3-azo- and 4-azoalkyd dyes obtained from *O. dalbergioides* oil incorporated 3-nitro- and 4-nitroalkyd resins by reduction, diazotisation and coupling with alkaline solution of phenolic compounds like α -/ β -naphthol and 8-hydroxyquinoline in ice-cold condition have decent shades like pale rose, dark crimson and dawn pink respectively. The dyes have been used as disperse dyes using Tween-80 as a dispersing agent on nylon and polyester fabrics. Dyed fabrics maintained their fastness on exposure to sunlight. The results (Table 4) reveal that the dyes have moderate exhaustion (55.2–59.5%) and good fixation (94.3–97.78%) for both the fabrics. The dyes were also successfully used for wool yarns.

Experimental

The dried and powdered *O. dalbergioides* seeds were extracted with petroleum-ether (b.p. 60–80°) in a soxhlet apparatus. The physicochemical properties of the oil were determined. The fatty acid composition of the oil was found out by glc analysis of the methyl esters of mixed fatty acids.

Nutritional study of fatty oil: Twenty albino rats (~80 g) of either sex were kept on constant diet

TABLE 4—EXHAUSTION AND FIXATION STUDY OF 3-AZO- AND 4-AZO ALKYD DYES*

Sl. no.	Coupling component	Colour of dye	Fabric used (g)	Amount of dye left in dye bath (a) mg	Amount of dye exhausted from dye bath (b)=10-(a) mg	% Dye exhausted from dye bath (100×b/10)	Amount of dye fixed on 1 g of fabric (c) mg	% Dye fixed on fabric c×100/b %
1	α-Naphthol	(a) Pale rose	Nylon	4.15	5.85	58.5	5.72	97.78
		(b) Pale rose	Nylon	4.25	5.75	57.5	5.48	95.30
2	β-Naphthol	(a) Dark crimson	Nylon	4.05	5.95	59.5	5.78	97.14
		(b) Light crimson	Nylon	4.10	5.90	59.0	5.62	95.25
3	8-Hydroxyquinolene	(a) Dawn pink	Nylon	4.30	5.70	57.0	5.45	95.61
		(b) Dawn pink	Nylon	5.35	5.65	56.5	5.35	94.69
4	α-Naphthol	(a) Pale rose	Polyester	4.05	5.95	59.5	5.78	94.14
		(b) Pale rose	Polyester	4.22	5.78	57.8	5.55	96.02
5	β-Naphthol	(a) Dark crimson	Polyester	4.15	5.85	58.5	5.60	95.73
		(b) Light crimson	Polyester	4.35	5.65	56.5	5.38	95.22
6	8-Hydroxyquinolene	(a) Dawn pink	Polyester	4.38	5.62	56.2	5.30	94.31
		(b) Dawn pink	Polyester	4.48	5.52	55.2	5.22	94.57

*(a) indicates 3-azo alkyd dye and (b) 4-azo alkyd dye.

for a month and then used. Ten rats randomly selected had free access to the basic diet mixed with 10% (w/v) oil. The experiment was continued for 60 days. The animals were weighed after 5 days and examined for abnormal signs like change in weight, loss of hairs, scaly tail, etc. At the end of 60 days all surviving animals were sacrificed. Blood was collected by heart puncture and liver was perfused with saline via the portal vein to remove as much of the trapped blood as possible and excised. The excised liver was quickly immersed in chloroform-methanol (2:1) mixture. Cholesterol of blood serum and liver was extracted by appropriate method⁵ and determined quantitatively by colorimetric estimation.

Polymerisation study of fatty oil : Thermal polymerisation of *O. dalbergioids* seed oil at different temperatures and for different time durations was carried out by the reported method⁶. Physicochemical properties, viz. density (at 30°), refractive index (at 80°), iodine value, intrinsic viscosity (η) (in CCl₄) and average molecular weight (\bar{M}_n) (by VPO using DMF as solvent) of the oil samples were evaluated at different temperatures and heating durations (Table 1), and temperature of 280° was chosen for polymerisation reaction. Aliquots (15 ml) of samples were drawn at different stages and the physicochemical parameters were determined (Table 2). The progress of polymerisation was also determined from IR spectra of each oil sample.

Preparation of alkyds and substituted 3-/4-nitro-alkyds : Preparation of alkyd and 3-/4-nitro substituted alkyds⁷ were carried out in two stages, i.e. glycerolysis of oil and transesterification with phthalic and 3-/4-nitrophthalic anhydrides. The various properties of prepared alkyd resins were determined (Table 3) and characterised from their IR spectra.

Azoalkyd dyes : Preparation and properties⁸ : The 3-/4-nitroalkyds obtained in the above preparations were separated in sodium bicarbonate soluble

and insoluble parts. The insoluble part was reduced with sodium hydrosulphite to 3-aminoalkyd resin. Then the dyes were prepared by diazotising with sodium nitrite and coupling with alkaline solution of phenolic compounds like α-/β-naphthol and 8-hydroxyquinolene in ice-cold condition.

The 3-/4-azoalkyd dyes thus obtained were applied on polyester and nylon fabrics as disperse dyes⁹ using Tween-80 as a dispersing agent. The exhaustion and fixation rate of the dyes were also determined (Table 4). The dyes were also tested on wool yarns.

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